

ELECTROMAGNETIC ANALYSIS OF BIOLOGICAL SIGNAL TRANSMISSION IN POLYGRAPHS: PHYSIOLOGY AND MEASUREMENT OF BODILY ELECTRICAL PULSES

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Abstract - A polygraph was developed to capture biological signals using electromagnetic principles to measure heart rate, skin temperature, and humidity. With the use of precise sensors, the device provides data on an individual's physical and emotional conditions. The effectiveness and signal interference were analyzed, highlighting the relevance of electromagnetism in biomedical engineering.

Keywords: Electromagnetism; Polygraph; Biological signals; Heart rate; Biomedical sensors.

INTRODUCTION

The human body, during its functioning, both in static and dynamic situations, generates variations in various forms of energy, including chemical, electrical, mechanical, and thermal energy. These variations are called biological signals [1]. The measurement of these signals can be performed using sensors that apply the principles of electromagnetism as described by Maxwell's Laws, thus enabling the creation of a polygraph capable of analyzing an individual's physical and emotional state.

Electrical signals, such as those generated by the heart, possess a resting electrical potential due to the concentrations of sodium and potassium ions in the intracellular and extracellular environments. As the concentration of these ions fluctuates, these potentials change; in other words, the entire electrical activity of the cell can be captured [2]. Body heat is detected by the resistive change in the sensor, where electrical resistance varies according to temperature, while humidity can be measured by the variation in the sensor's capacitance. These signals, which reflect biological and physiological activity, are captured and processed by devices based on electromagnetic principles, allowing for a detailed analysis of the individual's condition.

This article aims to develop a polygraph and investigate the electromagnetic fundamentals involved in the detection of biological signals, focusing on the measurement of temperature, humidity, and especially the electrical signals generated by heartbeats.

DEVELOPMENT

To understand the detection of biological signals used in polygraphs, it is essential to grasp how electrical signals are generated by cells.

1. Cellular Electrophysiology

Cellular electrophysiology is crucial for understanding the conduction of electrical signals, such as those in the heart. Cardiac cells maintain a resting electrical potential due to an unequal distribution of sodium (Na^+) and potassium (K^+) ions

between the intracellular and extracellular environments. During depolarization, the permeability of the cell membrane changes, allowing Na^+ to enter the intracellular space, reversing the electrical potential. Following this process, repolarization occurs, where K^+ ions exit into the extracellular space, restoring the resting electrical potential. This process results in cell contraction, with the electrical impulse being transmitted through the cardiac tissue [2].

Figure 1 - Cell at Resting Electric Potential

2. Cardiac Conduction System

The cardiac conduction system regulates the rhythm in which depolarization and repolarization of the cells occur, starting at the sinoatrial (SA) node. The SA node generates electrical impulses that cause atrial depolarization, which then spreads to the rest of the heart, resulting in a heartbeat [2].

3. Electrocardiographic Recording

The heart's electrical activity is recorded by electrodes or pulse and heartbeat sensors, producing an electrocardiogram (ECG). The waves in the ECG represent different parts of the cardiac cycle: the P wave (atrial depolarization), the QRS complex (ventricular depolarization), and the T wave (ventricular repolarization).

Figure 2 - Electrocardiographic Recording

4. Detection of Electrical Pulse

The electrocardiograph detects variations in electrical potential throughout the entire cardiac cycle, with each depolarization and repolarization generating electrical pulses. The sum of these pulses results in the ECG waves, representing the heart's electrical activity.

During the construction of the polygraph, an HDC1080 temperature and humidity sensor was used, which conducts measurements based on two principles: capacitance and resistance variation. For humidity detection, the sensor employs a hygroscopic dielectric material capable of interacting with the water present in the environment—specifically, in the case of the polygraph, the sweat of the individual being analyzed. The capacitance changes as water is absorbed, and this change is converted into an electrical signal, which is processed and transformed into a digital reading [3].

Figura 3 - Temperature and Humidity Sensor and Heartbeat Sensor

Using the differential form of Gauss's Law for electricity and its relation to capacitance, we observe that when the dielectric material changes, the permittivity (ϵ) — which represents how the medium interacts with an electric field — also changes. As a result, there is a variation in the divergence of the electric field for different permittivity values, leading to corresponding changes in capacitance based on the humidity of the dielectric material [5].

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \quad C = \frac{\epsilon A}{d}$$

Figure 4 - Gauss's Law for Electricity

Figure 5 - Formula for the Capacitance of a Parallel Plate Capacitor

E = Magnetic field
 ρ = Charge density

ϵ = Electric permittivity
 C = Capacitance
 A = Surface area of the capacitor plates
 d = Distance between the capacitor plates

For temperature measurement, the HDC1080 sensor uses a thermistor, which is a resistor whose resistance decreases as the temperature increases. This occurs due to thermal generation, which is responsible for breaking covalent bonds in a semiconductor crystal, releasing more free electrons in the material. The sensor measures this variation in resistance, and the integrated circuit converts the signal into a digital reading [4].

Using these sensors, a polygraph was built that monitors heartbeats, temperature, and humidity of the individual. From these variables, stress can be evaluated, as when the human body is under stress, an increase in body temperature is observed, heartbeats become more frequent and irregular, and humidity increases due to greater sweat production.

For the circuit assembly, an Arduino Uno was used along with pulse, heartbeat, temperature, and humidity sensors. The pulse and heartbeat sensor has three terminals: one for the positive power supply, another for the negative, and one for the analog output, which connects to the Arduino's analog input. The temperature and humidity sensor has four terminals: two for power, one clock pin for the I2C bus, which synchronizes communication between the sensor and Arduino, and the last pin for data, also on the I2C bus, through which data is transmitted between the sensor and the microcontroller. Unlike the pulse and heartbeat sensor, the HDC1080 uses only the Arduino's digital inputs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Signals Captured by the Pulse and Heartbeat Sensor

During the polygraph experiments, heart rate data was collected under different physiological conditions, such as rest and induced stress. The sensor was able to clearly capture the characteristic waves of the cardiac cycle. The average heart rate during the resting state ranged from 60 to 100 bpm (beats per minute), while in a stressful situation, it increased to 100 to 160 bpm, indicating a physical or mental alteration. These results confirm the sensor's effectiveness in accurately detecting the variations in electrical potential generated by the heart. However, signal interference was observed at certain moments, such as when the sensor's position on the skin affected signal capture. In other words, depending on the tissue, the signal reception varied. The best location identified for accurate signal capture was the upper part of the wrist.

Figure 5 - Graph of the signals captured by the pulse and heartbeat sensor with frequency variation

2. Temperature and Humidity Measurement

The measurements taken by the HDC1080 sensor showed a significant increase in both body temperature and humidity under stress conditions. The average temperature in the resting state was 36.5°C, with a minimal variation of $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$, while under stress, it rose to 37.2°C, with a variation of $\pm 0.3^\circ\text{C}$. Humidity also changed, from 45% with fluctuations of $\pm 5\%$ to 65% with variations of $\pm 4\%$.

However, temperature and humidity variations, especially humidity, respond less immediately compared to heart rate, making them less conclusive but complementary for analyzing stress levels over a longer period of time. These results align with the human body's physiological response to stress, where increased metabolic activity raises temperature and stimulates sweat production. One observed factor was that ambient temperature interfered with the measurements, causing slight variations in the results.

CONCLUSION

This article discussed the electromagnetic principles used to measure and process biological signals, particularly variations in the forms of energy generated by the human body. To understand the correlation between the electrical potential in human tissues and various forms of electricity in tissues, Maxwell's equations were applied to physiology through an in-depth literature review.

The article developed and examined a polygraph, a device capable of simultaneously measuring multiple biological signals, including electrical signals generated by the heart, as well as variations in skin temperature and humidity. It demonstrated how sensors, like the ECG, capture the electrical signals from the heart and process them to provide detailed information on cardiac activity.

The results showed that the electromagnetic model is reliable for measuring biological signals. Throughout the study, heartbeats were defined, and the importance of eliminating noise and distractions was emphasized. Comparisons with established literature and similar works validated the results, demonstrating the relevance of electromagnetism in the field of engineering.

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